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Research Article

**SYNTHESIS, CHARACTERIZATION AND EVALUATE THE
BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY OF SOME OF SUBSTITUTED
IMIDAZOLE DERIVATIVES****Thukuntla Ramya Krishna *¹, Dr.B. Sudhakar, Dr.K. Chaitanyaprasad,
Dr.K. Shravankumar**Department Of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Samskruti College Of Pharmacy, Ghatkesar,
Telangana. 501301.**Abstract:**

The preliminary studies on antimicrobial activity of the new imidazole derivatives have generated some interesting data. An attempt has been made to infer the ultimate outcome of the present studies basing on this data. The compounds were confirmed by TLC, melting point and spectral studies such as FT-IR, MS, and ¹H NMR. All the synthesized new imidazole derivatives were evaluated for antibacterial activity by using standard ciprofloxacin, antifungal activity by using standard fluconazole and antioxidant activity by using ascorbic acid.

*Synthetic work of the studies could go positively as per the planning and as such in all the reactions carried out. The expected compounds alone could be obtained. Newly synthesized compounds were characterized by TLC, IR, ¹H-NMR and Mass spectral analysis. New imidazole derivatives showed promising antimicrobial activity. Compounds **Methyl and Fluorine** imidazole derivatives were found to be the more potent antibacterial activity respectively towards gram positive (*Micrococcus luteus*) and gram negative (*klebsiella pneumonia*) New imidazole derivatives showed promising antioxidant activity. Compounds (**R=F**) & (**R=CH₃**) were found to be more potent antioxidant compounds among the all-test compounds.*

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INTRODUCTION:

Antimicrobial refers to a substance that either kills or stops the growth of microorganisms. Antimicrobial drugs may be grouped according to the germs they are most effective against [1-3]. Antibiotics and antifungals are a few of examples of therapies for bacteria and fungus. Microbial infection is one of the most common diseases that kills millions of people globally [3-5]. It is caused by several types of bacteria, viruses, and fungi.

The actions of bacteria have a profound influence on humans. Few of us appreciate how important microorganisms are to our daily lives. Their actions now and in the future have a significant impact on our ecosystem. We should not see microorganisms as separate from us since they fundamentally help us [7,8]. They are used in the production of a variety of items, including dairy products, certain foods, medications, pharmaceutical ingredients, and chemicals.

Despite the well-established useful roles that microorganisms play and their perhaps advantageous effects, it's probable that they are better known as the cause of human sickness and food spoilage. Jaundice, TB, typhoid, dermatomycoses, dysentery, malaria, herpes, legionnaire's disease, and influenza are a few conditions that might affect people. It has been discovered that both plants and animals may get microbial infections, just as people can. Additionally, microbes have had a significant impact on population change, conflict, and religion. Maintaining human convenience and comfort while halting the spread of illnesses, infections, pollution from decomposition, and spoiling that they produce depends on the regulation of the microbial population. Infectious diseases have always been a major cause of illness in humans, according to the history of disease. Microorganisms were not recognized as the primary cause of a number of infectious illnesses that had plagued mankind from the beginning of time until the second half of the 19th century [7–11]. In 1910, Ehrlich created salvarsan, the first antimicrobial antibiotic in recorded history, as a treatment for syphilis. Sulfonamides were created in 1935 by Domagk and other researchers. Since these medications were made from synthetic chemicals, there are some questions about their safety and effectiveness. In 1928, Fleming made the penicillin discovery. On culture plates, he observed that the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus* was inhibited around a contaminated blue mould (a fungus belonging to the *Penicillium* genus) [12, 13]. He reasoned that a bacterium would produce compounds that would stop other germs from growing.

In the 1940s, penicillin was initially used in medical settings. Penicillin, a unique drug in terms of its efficiency and safety, contributed to the survival of many injured soldiers during World War II and the development of antimicrobial chemotherapy. Over the course of the next two decades, many new antibacterial medication kinds were consecutively produced. Using the soil bacteria *Streptomyces griseus*, the aminoglycoside antibiotic streptomycin was developed in 1944. Later, microorganisms from the soil were used to generate chemicals including chloramphenicol, tetracycline, macrolide, and glycopeptide (similar to vancomycin). Nalidixic acid, a quinolone antibacterial medication, was created in 1962. Thanks to advancements in each kind of antibacterial agent, the antibacterial spectrum remained wider and the antimicrobial activity was higher. We'll use beta lactam antibiotics as an example. Some of the beta-lactam antibiotics include cepheems, monobactams, carbapenems, and penicillin. Penicillin was initially ineffective against *S. aureus* and other Gram-positive bacteria. Later, methicillin was created to treat *S. aureus* that was resistant to penicillin and manufactures the penicillin-hydrolyzing enzyme penicillinase [15–17]. Widening the antibacterial spectrum led to the development of ampicillin and piperacillin. Cepheems, which were created in the 1960s, are now widely used.

In recent years, fewer novel antimicrobials have been commercially available for human use worldwide. Between the introductions of nalidixic acid (1962) and linezolid (2000), No new classes of antimicrobials have been created in the last 37 years; rather, all antimicrobials that have hit the market during this time have been altered versions of compounds that already exist [18–21]. Pharmaceutical companies are less interested in developing novel antimicrobial treatments due to the high cost and time commitment. Anti-infective medication research and development might take 15 to 20 years and cost more than \$1 billion [19]. Market entry expenses for new products are rising by 10% annually. The bulk of significant pharmaceutical firms have completely stopped funding anti-infective research.

INTRODUCTION TO BACTERIA:

Antimicrobial refers to a chemical that either kills or inhibits the development of microbes. Antimicrobial medications may be categorized according to the bacteria they are most effective against. Antibiotics and antifungals are a few of examples of therapies for bacteria and fungus. Microbial infections are among the most common illnesses that kill millions of people

each year [22]. They are brought on by different kinds of bacteria, viruses, and fungi.

The activities of bacteria have a big influence on people. More than most of us realize, microorganisms play an important role in our everyday lives. Their actions now and in the future have had a significant influence on our ecosystem. Since microbes have a profoundly positive effect on people, they shouldn't be seen as distinct from us. They work in the production of a variety of items, such as dairy products, certain foods, medicines, medical agents, and chemicals [23–25].

Despite the well-established positive functions and maybe advantageous actions of microorganisms, it's probable that they are best recognized for being the cause of human sickness and food spoilage. Jaundice, TB, typhoid, dermatomycoses, dysentery, malaria, herpes, legionnaire's disease, and influenza are a few ailments that might affect humans [26, 27]. It has been discovered that both plants and animals may get microbial infections, just as people do. War, religion, and population movement have all been significantly impacted by microbes. When examining the history of human illness, infectious diseases historically accounted for a sizable portion of all illnesses, and the control of the microbial population is essential to maintaining human convenience and comfort while preventing the spread of diseases, infections, contamination from decomposition, and spoilage that they cause [28-31]. Many infectious illnesses that had plagued humanity from the beginning of time were not linked to microorganisms until the second half of the 19th century. In 1910, Ehrlich created salvarsan, the first antimicrobial antibiotic in recorded history, as a treatment for syphilis. Sulphonamides were created in 1935 by Domagk and other researchers. Due to the synthetic nature of these medications, there are some questions about their effectiveness and safety. In 1928, Fleming developed the penicillin discovery. On culture plates, he discovered that *Staphylococcus aureus* development was constrained in the vicinity of a contaminated blue mould (a fungus belonging to the *Penicillium* species). A bacteria would exude substances that might hinder the development of other organisms [32].

In the 1940s, penicillin was initially used in medical settings. Many handicapped troops survived World War II thanks to penicillin, a remarkable drug in terms of its safety and efficacy that also helped bring in the era of antimicrobial chemotherapy. Over the next two decades, new antimicrobial agent classes were gradually produced. Using the soil bacteria *Streptomyces griseus*, the aminoglycoside antibiotic streptomycin was developed in 1944. Later,

microorganisms from the soil were used to generate chemicals including chloramphenicol, tetracycline, macrolide, and glycopeptide (similar to vancomycin). Nalidixic acid, a quinolone antibacterial medication, was created in 1962 [33–35]. Thanks to advancements in each type of antibacterial agent, the antibacterial spectrum remained larger and the antimicrobial activity was greater. We'll use beta lactam antibiotics as an example. One class of beta-lactam antibiotics is penicillin, while others include monobactams, carbapenems, and cepheims. Gram-positive bacteria like *S. aureus* were initially penicillin-resistant. Later, methicillin was created to treat *S. aureus* that was resistant to penicillin and produced the penicillin-hydrolyzing enzyme penicillinase. Widening the antibacterial spectrum led to the development of ampicillin and piperacillin [36]. Cepheims are widely used nowadays and were created in the 1960s [37]. In recent years, fewer novel antimicrobials have been readily accessible for human use worldwide. Between the release of nalidixic acid (1962) and linezolid (2000), 37 years, no new classes of antimicrobials were created; all antimicrobials launched during this period were alterations to the already-existing compounds. Pharmaceutical businesses are less interested in developing new antimicrobial agents since it is so costly and time-consuming [38]. Anti-infective medication research and development may take 15 to 20 years and cost more than \$1 billion. Market entry expenses for new products are rising by 10% annually. Most significant pharmaceutical firms have completely ceased funding anti-infective research [39–40].

Mechanisms of action of antibacterial agents

A. Interfering with the cytoplasmic membrane: substances (Polymyxins, Daptomycin) permeate the cell wall and outer membrane of vulnerable cells to reach the cytoplasmic membrane. The cytoplasmic membrane is disrupted and rendered unstable when they adhere to it. This results in cell death (they are bactericidal) as a consequence of cytoplasm leakage [42–48].

B. There are two categories of medications that interfere with the production of nucleic acids: By inhibiting the enzyme DNA gyrase, fluoroquinolone drugs (such as nalidixic acid, ciprofloxacin, levofloxacin, and gemifloxacin) interfere with DNA synthesis. In order to cause cell death, fluoroquinolones bind to the DNA gyrase-DNA complex and allow the broken DNA strands to escape into the cell [42–48]. They are bactericidal. Rifampin binds to DNA-in need of RNA polymerase, which prevents the creation of RNA and kills cells.

C. Interfering with the synthesis of cell walls: The -Lactams, such as carbapenems, monobactams,

penicillins, and cephalosporins, and the glycopeptides, as well as vancomycin and teicoplanin, are antibacterial therapies that work by attempting to block bacterial cell wall synthesis. By interfering with the enzymes required for the synthesis of the peptidoglycan coat, β -lactam mediators prevent the formation of the bacterial cell wall. By connecting to the terminal D-alanine residues of developing peptidoglycan series, glycopeptides also obstruct the formation of the cell wall and prevent the cross-linking stages necessary for the formation of a strong cell wall (they are bactericidal) [43].

D. Reserve of a metabolic pathway: Sulphonamides and trimethoprim prevent the synthesis of folic acid, which at first prevents DNA synthesis. Trimethoprim, which resembles folic acid chemically, and additional sulfamethoxazole (sulphonamide), a typical antibacterial medication combination, block two stages in the enzymatic pathway for bacterial folate synthesis (they are bacteriostatic) [46].

E. Protein synthesis inhibition: Tetracyclines, aminoglycosides, Macrolides, and oxazolidinones, in addition to chloramphenicol, produce their antibacterial actions specifically by inhibiting protein synthesis. The ribosomes in bacteria are not identical to their counterparts in eukaryotic cells in terms of configuration. To selectively halt bacterial growth, antibacterial mediators take use of these variations. Chloramphenicol binds to the 50S subunit of the ribosome, while aminoglycosides, tetracyclines, and macrolides bind to the 30S subunit (they are bacteriostatic) [48, 49].

INTRODUCTION OF HETEROCYCLIC GROUPS:

Each week, organic chemists produce hundreds of unique heterocyclic molecules. In most cases, a chemist has a specific reason for developing a certain substance, which is often motivated by theoretical considerations, biological processes, medicinal chemistry, or a combination of all three. The heterocyclic compounds are widely distributed in nature and are essential to all living things. They exhibit an essential role in the metabolism of all living cells [50]. Due to their widespread distribution in nucleic acid strands and their participation in almost every physiological activity of plants and animals, nitrogen heterocycles are the most prevalent among the huge number of heterocycles found in nature, particularly those incorporating oxygen or sulphur. Heterocyclic compounds have several applications in both business and daily life [51–54]. For instance, the majority of sugars and their derivatives, with the exception of vitamin C, have a five- or six-membered ring with one oxygen atom in the formula (Furanosid

structure or Pyranose structure, respectively) [54]. Additionally, the majority of vitamin B group members have heterocyclic rings containing nitrogen. For instance, vitamin B6 (pyridoxine), which is generated from the pyridine, is necessary for the metabolism of amino acids [55–56]. The heterocyclic compounds play a significant role in the medicine and pharmaceutical industries as well. Due to their unique chemical reactivity, about 80% of medicines now in use have a heterocyclic foundation. The majority of medications entering pharmacopeias are heterocyclic substances, including the tranquilizer chlordiazepoxide, the antidepressant imipramine, the hypertension guanethidine, the diuretic and antihypertensive indapamide, etc. Numerous antibiotics include heterocyclic rings, including penicillin, cephalosporin, norfloxacin, streptomycin, and others [57–59]. As wide spectrum anthelmintics, several veterinary medicines, such as pyrantel and morantel, are the preferred medication. Atrazine and Simazine, two well-known herbicides, are examples of heterocyclic agricultural compounds. Plant pigments with heterocyclic rings, including indigo, hemoglobin, anthocyanins, and chlorophyll, have made significant contributions to color chemistry. Numerous additional heterocyclic coloring substances have also been in use since ancient times. Additionally, the ionic molecular crystal of heterocyclic tetra Seleno fulvalene was the first to exhibit superconductivity. One of the most active areas of organic chemistry study is heterocyclic chemistry, which is expanding quickly. In 1998, published research on the creation of heterocyclic compounds made up about 60% of all available organic chemistry literature. Today, however, this percentage is much higher due to the availability of novel heterocyclic compounds in a variety of fields, including materials science, biochemistry, pharmaceuticals, and others [55].

Heterocyclic molecules are cyclic mixtures of carbon with other atoms including oxygen, nitrogen, and sulfur. Pyrrole, furan, and thiophene are examples of heterocyclic compounds with a single heteroatom, whereas azole, pyrrole, thiazole, thiadiazole, oxadiazole, triazene, and other heterocyclic molecules have several heteroatoms. Heterocyclic compounds come in a wide variety, and many of them have therapeutic value [52, 57].

INTRODUCTION TO IMIDAZOLE:

Imidazole is an organic compound is a cyclic, planar molecule that consists of a five-membered ring containing three carbons and two nitrogens, with the nitrogens arranged in the 1st and 3rd positions. The nitrogen in 2 the 1st position is a “pyrrole” type

nitrogen and the nitrogen in the 3rd position is a “pyridine” type nitrogen.

Imidazole was first reported by Heinrich Debus³ in 1858, fully developed by Radziszewski the beginning of 1882 and further modified by Weidenhagen in 1935. It is the synthesis of an imidazole derivative by the condensation of α -dicarbonyl compound (e.g. glyoxal), an aldehyde and two equivalents of dry ammonia in alcohol. Therefore, this reaction is generally known as Radziszewski reaction and occasionally called as Radziszewski synthesis, Weidenhagen synthesis or Debus-Radziszewski imidazole synthesis.

EXPERIMENTAL

4.1 Chemicals and Reagents

Chemicals and reagents used in the research work were of AR and LR grade and procured from Astron

Chemicals, Ahmedabad Lobachemie Private Limited, Mumbai Krishna chemical Industry, Vadodara Merck specialities Private Limited, Mumbai
The chemicals were used as obtained.

4.2 Analytical Techniques

4.2.1 Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC): Compounds purity were checked by using Silica gel G coated aluminium plates/Merck Silica gel as stationary phase and various combinations of ethyl acetate, n-hexane, methanol, toluene, benzene as mobile phase. The spots on TLC plates were visualized under ultraviolet lamp and/or by using iodine chamber.

4.2.2 Physical data: Open capillary method was used to determine the melting point of synthesized compounds and were uncorrected.

4.3 Instruments Characterization of synthesized compounds were carried out by IR spectra, Mass spectra, NMR spectra.

4.3.1 Infra-Red spectra: FTIR DRS 8400, Shimadzu were used to record IR spectra of synthesized compounds as KBr pellets in the range of 4000 – 500 cm^{-1} .

4.3.2 ^1H Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectra: ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on Varian 400 MHz spectrometer in DMSO solvent.

4.3.3 Mass Spectra: Mass spectra were obtained using 2010EV LCMS Shimadzu instrument. Mass spectra were recorded on Agilent MS ion trap system.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

Scheme:

Step-1: Synthesis of dione from benzaldehyde

The reaction is only performed in aqueous buffer with low substrate concentrations (maximum of 20 mM benzaldehyde) with space-time-yields. To increase the productivity of this cascade, the enzyme concentration was optimized and its performance in the presence of higher benzaldehyde concentrations was investigated.

Step-2: Dione synthesis from synthesis from α -anilino acetophenones:

When the multicomponent condensation reaction was carried out at 80°C using 5 and 10 mol% of pTSA in ethanol, we obtained only 24 and 20% yields respectively in 10 h. Further investigation was carried out using 5 and 10 mol % of CAN as a catalyst for the condensation reaction over 10 h yields only 47 and 43% of products,

respectively

Chemical Formula: $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2$

Chemical Formula: $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_2$

Chemical Formula: $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{21}\text{FN}_2$

Chemical Formula: $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{21}\text{ClN}_2$

Chemical Formula: $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{21}\text{BrN}_2$

Chemical Formula: $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{21}\text{IN}_2$

Chemical Formula: $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{23}\text{FN}_2$

Chemical Formula: $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{23}\text{ClN}_2$

Chemical Formula: $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{23}\text{BrN}_2$

Chemical Formula: $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{23}\text{IN}_2$

METHODS OF IDENTIFICATION:

1. Melting point
2. TLC
3. Infrared Spectroscopy
4. Nuclear Magnetic Resonance
5. Mass Spectroscopy.

The synthesized compounds were identified by using following method

Melting point:

The melting point of the compounds is determined by the capillary tube method. The synthesized compounds were start losing their crystallinity at a particular temperature.

Thin layer chromatography:-

Pre-coated TLC plates with silica gel GF 250 are used. Samples of reactants and products are prepared with suitable solvents.

The characterization was carried out using sophisticated methods like Infra-red spectroscopy, Nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy and Mass spectroscopy.

Infrared Spectroscopy:

One of the most potent analytical methods, infrared spectroscopy allows for the potential of chemical identification. The most significant benefit of using infrared spectroscopy over other common methods of structural research is how rapidly it may provide vital details about the functional groups present in the molecule. The approach is based on the straightforward observation that a chemical compound exhibits pronounced, selective infrared absorption. A chemical compound's molecules absorb infrared radiation and then vibrate slightly, creating tightly packed absorption bands known as the IR absorption spectrum, which can span a large wavelength range. The distinctive functional groups and bonds that are present in a chemical material correspond to a number of bands that are present in the IR spectra. A chemical compound's IR spectrum can be used as a fingerprint to identify it. By employing a potassium bromide pellet method and an FT-IR spectrometer, the infrared spectra of the produced derivatives was recorded.

Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy:

This area of spectroscopy involves the use of radiofrequency waves to cause changes in the magnetic energy levels of molecule nuclei. Nuclei kept in a magnetic field produce the magnetic energy levels. The energy level shift is impossible without the magnetic field because the spin states of nuclei are degenerated, or have the same

energy. The use of an external magnetic field, which necessitates various types of Rf radiation to bring them into resonance, allows for the energy level change. This phenomenon can be measured. It is an effective instrument for looking at the structure of nuclei. Tetra methyl silane was used as the internal standard in ¹H NMR spectra of the synthesised derivatives, which were performed using Bruker spectrometers operating at 400-MHz and 500-MHz. Dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) was used as the solvent for a ¹H NMR spectrum, and the chemical shift data were shown as delta values linked to trimethyl silane (TM) in ppm.

Mass spectroscopy:

There are three key tasks that a mass spectrometer must do. A stream of highly energetic electrons is used to first bombard molecules, turning some of them into ions that are subsequently accelerated by an electric field. Second, under an electric or magnetic field, the accelerated ions are split based on their mass to charge ratios. Finally, a device that can count the number of ions impacting it is used to identify the ions that have a specific mass-to-charge ratio. The output of the detector is enhanced and supplied to a recorder. The trace from the recorder is a graph of observed particles as a function of mass-to-charge ratio, or mass spectrum. Using an MSD spectrometer, the mass of the synthesised chemical was measured.

**PHARMACOLOGICAL EVALUATIONS
ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF
SYNTHESISED COMPOUNDS:**

Antibacterial activity by Agar Well Diffusion method by measuring the zone of inhibition in mm.

Materials:

- Nutrient Broth Media
- Nutrient Agar media
- Dimethyl sulfoxide
- Ciprofloxacin
- Distilled water

Test Organisms:

Gram positive	Gram negative
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
<i>Micrococcus luteus</i>	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>

Nutrient media Composition:

Beef extract	: 3 grams
Peptone	: 5 grams
Sodium chloride	: 5 grams
Agar agar	: 15 grams

Distilled Water : 1000 liters
pH : 7.4±0.2

Preparation of bacterial cultures for assay:

The test organisms were sub cultured using nutrient broth medium. The tubes containing sterilized media were inoculated with respective bacterial strains. After incubation at 37±1°C for 24 hours, they were stored in refrigerator. The stock cultures were maintained. Bacterial inoculums were prepared by transferring a loop full of culture to nutrient broth in conical flasks. The flasks were incubated at 37±1°C for 48 hours before the experiment.

Test sample preparation:

The test compounds were prepared for assay by dissolving them in dimethyl sulfoxide in required concentrations making 50µg/ml, 100µg/ml, 500µg/ml, and 1000µg/ml respectively for evaluation. A reference standard for both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria Ciprofloxacin was made in same concentrations as test compounds where dimethyl sulfoxide as control.

Assay by Agar well diffusion method:

By using the well diffusion method, test compounds' antibacterial susceptibility was evaluated. About 25ml of the sterilized (autoclaved at 120°C for 20min) nutrient agar medium was added to sterile Petri dishes, and the plates were set aside for the agar to solidify. By applying the bacterial suspension (1ml/100ml, or cfu/ml) to the surface of the agar plates with a sterile L-shaped glass rod, bacterial lawns were created. On the agar plates, wells were made using a sterile borer (6mm). The prepared test sample concentrations (100 g/ml, 500 g/ml, and 1000 g/ml), together with the control, were aseptically put into wells measuring about 50 l. To ensure that the solution diffused effectively into the nutrient agar medium, the plates were left in the refrigerator undisturbed for at least two hours. The plates were then incubated for a further 24 hours at 37°C. After the incubation period, the diameter of the inhibition zone in each well was manually measured using a millimeter scale, and the results were tabulated. The entire experiment was run in duplicate. To investigate the impact of the solvent on bacteria, dimethyl sulfoxide was kept constant as a control.

ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY (IN VITRO)

Materials:

Ascorbic acid : (Analytical grade, Merck India)
Methanol : (HPLC grade, Merck India)
DPPH : (α, α -diphenyl, β -picryl hydrazyl) (Sigma Aldrich)
Test compounds,
Double Distilled water.

Preparation of Standard Solution of Ascorbic Acid:

Required amount of Ascorbic acid was accurately weighed and dissolved in distilled water to prepare 1mM stock solution. Solutions of different concentrations (1nM, 3nM, 10nM, 30nM, 1µM, 3µM, 10µM, 30µM, 100µM, 300µM, 1mM) were prepared.

Preparation of DPPH Solution:

0.5mM solution of DPPH was prepared by dissolving the 19.71mg of DPPH in 100ml of methanol. The solution was protected from sunlight to prevent the oxidation of DPPH.

Preparation of Test Compounds:

Required amount of test compounds was dissolved in methanol and 1mM stock solution was prepared. Solutions of concentration ranging from 1nM to 1mM were prepared.

Principle:

The method is based on principle described by Blois (1958) method. The model of scavenging the DPPH radical is most widely used method to evaluate the anti-oxidant activity in relatively shorter time compared with other methods. The effect of anti-oxidant on DPPH radical scavenging was thought to be their hydrogen donating ability (Baumann *et al.*, 2002).

DPPH is a stable free radical that accepts an electron or hydrogen radical to become a stable diamagnetic molecule. The reduction capability of DPPH radical was determined by the decrease

in its absorbance at 517nm induced by anti-oxidants. The absorption maximum of stable DPPH radical in methanol was at 517nm. The decrease in absorbance of DPPH radical caused by anti-oxidants, because of the reaction between anti-oxidant molecules and radical, progresses, which result in the scavenging of the radical by hydrogen donation. Hence, DPPH is used as a substrate to evaluate the anti-oxidant activity.

Procedure:

To 2.8ml of test sample/ascorbic acid, 0.2ml of DPPH solution was added, mixed thoroughly and absorbance was measured at 517nm against blank, prepared in an identical way but without the test compound. The results were plotted on a graph and IC50 value was calculated.

$\text{inhibition} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of blank} - \text{Absorbance of}}{\text{Absorbance of blank}} \times 100$

Absorbance of blank X 100

IC₅₀ values of standard and synthesised molecules:

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

- ❑ The preliminary studies on antimicrobial activity of the new imidazole derivatives have generated some interesting data. An attempt has been made to infer the ultimate outcome of the present studies basing on this data.
- ❑ The compounds were confirmed by TLC, melting point and spectral studies such as FT-IR, MS, and ¹H NMR.
- ❑ All the synthesized new imidazole derivatives were evaluated for antibacterial activity by using standard ciprofloxacin, antifungal activity by using standard fluconazole and antioxidant activity by using ascorbic acid.
- ❑ **ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY:**

All the new imidazole derivatives employed in the antimicrobial activity. All the test compounds were prepared for assay by dissolving them in DMSO in required quantity in concentrations making 100µg/ml, 500 µg/ml and 1000µg/ml respectively for evaluation of antibacterial activity against gram positive and gram negative bacteria. Ciprofloxacin used as standard.

Bacteria:

Gram positive

Staphylococcus aureus
Micrococcus luteus

Gram negative

Escherichia coli
Klebsiella pneumonia

- Among all the synthesized compounds the following shown high activity for **antibacterial activity** when comparing with standard ciprofloxacin **Flourine And methyl derivatives are found to have promising antibacterial activity.**

ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY

- The IC₅₀ values of all synthesized test compounds were found between for compounds and standard with different concentrations
- All the compounds were tested at 1nM to 1mM concentrations and results were compared with standard drug (Ascorbic acid) at the same concentrations.
- Among these compounds, compound F & CH₃ showed (**Flourine and methyl**) effective antioxidant activity.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

Broadly the following conclusion could be drawn from the results of these investigations.

- Synthetic work of the studies could go positively as per the planning and as such in all the reactions carried out. The expected compounds alone could be obtained.
- Newly synthesized compounds were characterized by TLC, IR, ¹H-NMR and Mass spectral analysis.
- New imidazole derivatives showed promising antimicrobial activity. Compounds **Methyl and Flourine** imidazole derivatives were found to be the more potent antibacterial activity respectively towards gram positive (*Micrococcus luteus*) and gram negative (*klebsiella pneumonia*)
- New imidazole derivatives showed promising antioxidant activity. Compounds (**R=F**) & (**R= CH₃**) were found to be more

potent antioxidant compounds among the all-test compounds.

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